

Rhenium chemistry of pyridyldiazoles : oxygen atom transfer, oxidation, substitution and twin isomerization involving oxo, phosphine oxide and phosphine coordination^ψ

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Abstract : The pyridyldiazoles (L) used are 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole and 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole. The oxygen atom transfer reaction of [ReOCl₃(L)] with PPh₂R (R = Ph, Me) and Ph₂P(CH₂)_xPPh₂ (PxP, x = 1-4) has afforded *meridional* [Re(OPPh₂R)Cl₃(L)] and [Re(OPxP)Cl₃(L)] respectively. These (R = Ph, x = 1) are oxidised by HNO₃ yielding [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(L)]ReO₄ and [Re(OPiP)Cl₃(L)]ReO₄. Treatment of [Re(OPPh₂R)Cl₃(L)] with PPh₂R has furnished *facial* [Re(PPh₂R)Cl₃(L)]. The [Re(OPxP)Cl₃(L)] species undergo spontaneous twin isomerization in solution leading to [Re(PxPO)Cl₃(L)]. All compounds have been characterized with the help of spectral and electrochemical data. The X-ray structure of a [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(L)]ReO₄ complex is reported. The rates and activation parameters of oxygen atom transfer and twin isomerization reactions have been determined and reaction models proposed.

Keywords : Oxygen atom transfer, pyridyldiazoles, rhenium.

As part of our program in the design and reactivity of new oxorhenium(V) reagents based on *N,N*-chelation by conjugated nitrogen donor ligands¹, we recently reported the synthesis and characterization of the Re^VO complexes **1** and **2** incorporating chelation of 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole(pyod) and 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole(pytd) respectively². A notable reaction of oxorhenium(V) species is oxygen atom transfer to oxophilic substrates³⁻¹⁰ such as phosphines.

1, E=O, [Re^VOCl₃(pyod)]

2, E=S, [Re^VOCl₃(pytd)]

The availability of **1** and **2** has given an opportunity to explore their oxygen atom transfer behaviour towards tertiary phosphines. Both mono and diphosphines have

been used. The rates of oxygen atom transfer have been determined and trends thereof scrutinized. The phosphine oxide complexes have been isolated and characterized including structure determination of a rhenium(IV) system generated via metal oxidation. Coordinated phosphine oxides are replaceable by tertiary phosphines but with geometrical isomerization. In the case of diphosphines this phenomenon becomes intramolecular leading to twin isomerization. The effects of spacer length and metal oxidation state on the rate of twin isomerization is scrutinized and rationalized.

Results and discussion

Reactions and products :

The two tertiary monophosphines used in the present work are PPh₂R (R = Ph, Me). The four diphosphines utilized are of type **3** which will be abbreviated as PxP. The violet coloured phosphine oxide complexes **4/5** were obtained in excellent yields by reacting **1/2** with PPh₂R

^ψDedicated to the memory of Professor Pulinbihari Sarkar (1894-1971) who notably enriched rhenium chemistry.

in dichloromethane solution at room temperature, eq. (1).
The dark violet diphosphorus species 6/7

resulted from the reaction of 1/2 with three-fold excess of 3 (the excess is required to avoid formation of dinuclear species).

4, E=O, [Re^{III}(OPPh₂R)Cl₃(pyod)]

5, E=S, [Re^{III}(OPPh₂R)Cl₃(pytd)]

6, E=O, [Re^{III}(OPxP)Cl₃(pyod)]

7, E=S, [Re^{III}(OPxP)Cl₃(pytd)]

Electrochemical experiments (*vide infra*) revealed that the rhenium(IV) congeners of 4-7 can be electrogenerated in solution. This prompted us to examine their chemical oxidation. Indeed 4/5 (R = Ph) was readily oxidised by 0.1 N HNO₃ in acetonitrile solution furnishing in excellent yields 1 : 1 electrolytic 8/9 as yellow solids. It is unclear how the ReO₄⁻ anion originate from the starting material but this behaviour has precedence in rhenium chemistry^{11,12}. Of the complexes of type 6 and 7 the x = 1 species were similarly oxidised by nitric acid affording the salts 10 and 11.

Treatment of a solution of 4/5 with six-fold excess of PPh₂R in boiling benzene furnished green coloured 12/

8, E=O, [Re^{IV}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)]ReO₄

9, E=S, [Re^{IV}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄

10, E=O, [Re^{IV}(OP1P)Cl₃(pyod)]ReO₄

11, E=S, [Re^{IV}(OP1P)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄

13 in excellent yields, eq. (2). The reaction is attended with geometrical

isomerization (*mer* → *fac*). The phosphine oxide complexes of type 6/7 are stable in the solid state but undergo spontaneous transformation in dichloromethane solution with colour change from violet to green. Here the dangling phosphine function displaces the coordinated phosphine oxide function affording 14/15 in good yield. This transformation involves both linkage

12, E=O, [Re^{III}(PPh₂R)Cl₃(pyod)]

13, E=S, [Re^{III}(PPh₂R)Cl₂(pytd)]

14, E=O, [Re^{III}(PxPO)Cl₃(pyod)]

15, E=S, [Re^{III}(PxPO)Cl₃(pytd)]

(Re – OP → Re – PO) and geometrical (*mer* → *fac*) isomerization.

In all twentyeight compounds spanning the types 4-15 have been synthesized and characterized using spectral and electrochemical data in particular. Only representative results will be reported in this paper and selected data are listed in the Experimental Section. The complete set of data and results are available elsewhere¹³.

Spectra :

In IR the phosphine oxide complexes (4-11) incorporating the ReOP moiety display a strong P=O stretch within the region 1120–1135 cm⁻¹. Interestingly in 14 and 15 having an uncoordinated dangling P=O function the stretching frequency is significantly higher : 1186–1188 cm⁻¹. A characteristic Re–O stretch of the ReO₄⁻ anion in 8-11 occur near 905 cm⁻¹.

The phosphine oxide complexes (4-7) display two main bands in the visible region near 720 and 480 nm associated with a number of shoulders. These are believed to be of MLCT origin. The spectra are of diagnostic value and have been employed in rate studies (*vide infra*). Upon metal oxidation (as in 8-11) the MLCT bands disappear and the lowest energy band now occurs near 450 nm.

The phosphine complexes (12-15) show several bands in the visible region with a prominent feature near 680 nm. This is assigned to MLCT excitation and is believed to correspond to the band near 720 nm in the phosphine oxide species noted above. The blue shift in going from phosphine oxide to phosphine complexes is consistent with the extra stabilization of the *t*_{2g} shell by the phosphine donor.

The phosphine oxide complexes of types 4 and 5 have magnetic moments near 2μ_B as in several other rhenium(III) species⁷ and their ¹H NMR spectra are found to be paramagnetically shifted. Three relatively broad bands each representing one proton are shifted particularly strongly, the chemical shifts lying within the ranges 26 to 28, 22 to 25 and -3 to +1 ppm. These signals are believed to originate from the pyridyl ring coordinated to the metal. There are five signals (three doublets and two triplets) in the region 10.7 to 6.3 ppm each corresponding to one proton. One of these signal, presumably a doublet belongs to the coordinated pyridyl fragment and the remaining four to the pendant pyridine fragment. The phosphine aromatic proton signals occur as multiplets in the region 8.50 to 6.50 ppm. In the NMR spectra of the diphosphorus species 6 and 7 signals occur in the region 29 to -11 ppm. The spectra are however relatively com-

plex and no attempts were made to analyze them.

The protons of the rhenium(IV) systems 8 and 9 also display large shifts. Three one-proton signals occur near 60, -71 and -95 ppm. The remaining signals including those of the phosphine ligands occur within the range 11 to 2 ppm. No spin-spin structure is resolved. The spectra of [Re^{III}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)] and [Re^{IV}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄ are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectra of (a) [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)] and (b) [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄ in CDCl₃ solution

Lastly, in the phosphine chelates 12 and 13 the pyridyldiazole resonances occur in the range -4 to 24 ppm and the aromatic phosphine protons in the range 8 to 16 ppm.

Metal redox :

The complexes are uniformly electroactive in acetonitrile solution. The phosphine oxide systems 4-7 display a quasireversible (peak-to-peak separation 75–90 mV) one-electron response corresponding to the Re^{IV}/Re^{III} couple having *E*_{1/2} near 0.30 V versus SCE. The rhenium(IV) species 8 and 9 have the same voltammograms (opposite scan direction) as 4 and 5.

In the phosphine complexes 12-15 the Re^{IV}/Re^{III} reduction potentials lie near 0.65 V with peak-to-peak separation of 75–90 mV. The increase in the reduction potential in the phosphine complexes is consistent with the stabilization of *t*_{2g} shell via back-bonding to phosphorus. Significantly, in structurally characterized rhenium(III) complexes incorporating other types of *N,N*-chelation¹ the reduction potential in the phosphine oxide (*meridional*) and phosphine (*facial*) species display similar trends.

Structure of $[\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$:

None of the trivalent complexes afforded single crystals suitable for structure determination. However, their gross geometries as in 4-7 and 12-15 are beyond doubt in view of their spectral and electrochemical properties vis-a-vis those of related structurally characterized systems¹.

The asymmetric unit in the crystalline oxidised complex $[\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$ consists of two metrically similar but crystallographically distinct molecules : Molecule 1 and Molecule 2, Fig. 2 (cation only). Crystal data are collected in Table 1 and selected bond parameters are listed in Table 2.

Molecule 1

Molecule 2

Fig. 2. Perspective view of $[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for $[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{23}\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{PSRe}_2$
Formula weight	1061.30
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> , Å	15.295(3)
<i>b</i> , Å	16.328(3)
<i>c</i> , Å	16.619(3)
α , deg	80.17(3)
β , deg	63.59(3)
γ , deg	66.92(3)
<i>V</i> , Å ³	3419.6(12)
<i>Z</i>	4
ρ_{calcd} , mg m ⁻³	2.061
μ , mm ⁻¹	7.460
<i>R</i> 1	0.0817
<i>wR</i> 2	0.2206

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å), angles (deg) for $[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$

	Molecule 1	Molecule 2	
	Distances		
Re1-O1	1.986(12)	Re51-O51	2.005(11)
Re1-N1	2.146(14)	Re51-N51	2.128(13)
Re1-N2	2.117(13)	Re51-N52	2.08(2)
Re1-Cl1	2.299(4)	Re51-Cl51	2.299(5)
Re1-Cl2	2.323(5)	Re51-Cl52	2.320(5)
Re1-Cl3	2.318(5)	Re51-Cl53	2.335(4)
O1-P1	1.544(12)	O51-P51	1.518(12)
Re2-O2	1.14(7)	Re52-O52	1.45(2)
Re2-O3	1.60(2)	Re52-O53	1.56(3)
Re2-O4	1.41(4)	Re52-O54	1.51(2)
Re2-O5	1.55(2)	Re52-O55	1.47(3)
Angles			
O1-Re1-N1	169.5(5)	O51-Re51-N51	169.0(5)
O1-Re1-N2	94.6(5)	O51-Re51-N52	92.4(5)
O1-Re1-Cl1	94.2(4)	O51-Re51-Cl51	94.9(4)
O1-Re1-Cl2	92.6(4)	O51-Re51-Cl52	92.4(4)
O1-Re1-Cl3	88.8(4)	O51-Re51-Cl53	90.2(4)
N1-Re1-Cl1	95.9(4)	N51-Re51-Cl51	96.0(4)
N1-Re1-Cl2	89.3(4)	N51-Re51-Cl52	88.8(4)
N1-Re1-Cl3	88.2(4)	N51-Re51-Cl53	88.0(4)
N1-Re1-N2	75.2(5)	N51-Re51-N52	76.7(5)
N2-Re1-Cl1	171.2(4)	N52-Re51-Cl51	172.7(4)
N2-Re1-Cl2	85.7(4)	N52-Re51-Cl52	87.9(4)
N2-Re1-Cl3	88.2(4)	N52-Re51-Cl53	88.5(4)
Cl1-Re-Cl2	94.6(2)	Cl51-Re51-Cl52	92.9(2)

Table-2 (contd.)

Cl1-Re-Cl3	91.3(2)	Cl51-Re51-Cl53	90.3(2)
Cl2-Re-Cl3	173.8(2)	Cl52-Re51-Cl53	175.7(2)
Re1-O1-P1	149.5(8)	Re51-O51-P51	152.8(8)
O2-Re2-O3	104(2)	O52-Re52-O53	81(2)
O2-Re2-O4	122(4)	O52-Re52-O54	132(2)
O2-Re2-O5	121(4)	O52-Re52-O55	111(3)
O3-Re2-O4	122(3)	O53-Re52-O54	114(2)
O3-Re2-O5	109.2(14)	O53-Re52-O55	119(3)
O4-Re2-O5	77(3)	O54-Re52-O55	101(3)

In the distorted octahedral ReOCl_3N_2 coordination sphere of the cation the chloride ligands are meridionally disposed. The chelate ring makes a virtually perfect plane (mean deviation $< 0.01 \text{ \AA}$) in Molecule 1 and a very good plane (mean deviation 0.03 \AA) in Molecule 2. Indeed the whole $\text{Re}(\text{pytd})$ fragment is reasonably planar in both molecules (mean deviations 0.06 and 0.04 \AA respectively) meaning that the pendant pyridyl group is approximately coplanar with the rest of the $\text{Re}(\text{pytd})$ fragment. The relevant dihedral angles are 8.4° (Molecule 1) and 3.2° (Molecule 2).

The average Re-O, Re-Cl, Re-N(pyridyl) and Re-N(diazole) distances are 2.00 , 2.32 , 2.14 and 2.10 \AA respectively which compare well with those in rhenium(IV) pyridylazolate chelate⁸. The corresponding average distances in $[\text{Re}^{\text{III}}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{N},\text{N})]$ species studied in this laboratory¹ are 2.04 , 2.35 , 2.02 and 1.99 \AA respectively. The Re-O and Re-Cl distances are thus shorter in the oxidised complex. These bonds are primarily σ in character and the contraction of the metal radius upon oxidation is consistent with the trend of bond lengths. In contrast the average Re-N distances are significantly longer in the $[\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]^+$ complex.

Trivalent rhenium is a potent π -donor^{14,15} and metal oxidation is expected to diminish the donor power significantly. The longer Re-N bonds in the oxidised complex is believed to reflect the weakness or absence of back-bonding in the $\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}(\text{pytd})$ fragment.

The ReO_4^- anions have distorted tetrahedral geometries. The thermal parameters of ReO_4^- oxygen atoms are relatively high indicating the presence of considerable disorder. Average Re-O distances and O-Re-O angles are 1.43 \AA and 109.2° (Molecule 1) and 1.50 \AA and 109.7° (Molecule 2).

Oxygen atom transfer :

The rate of the transfer reaction stated in eq. (1) has been spectrophotometrically determined in dichloromethane solution in the cases of PPh_3 (302–308 K) and PPh_2Me (302 K). Time evolution spectra are characterized by multiple isosbestic points as in Fig. 3. Under

Fig. 3. Time evolution spectra for the reaction of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ with PPh_3 in CH_2Cl_2 solution at 302 K.

pseudo-first-order conditions (excess PPh_2R) the rates are proportional to the concentration of the oxo complex and the observed rate constant k_{obs} is proportional to the concentration of PPh_2R . The rate law is thus second-order eq. (3) where L is pyod/pytd. Rate data are collected in

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{L})] \\ &= k [\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{L})][\text{PPh}_2\text{R}] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Tables 3 and 4. Variable temperature rate data (PPh_3) followed the Eyring equation. The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for pyod and pytd species are respectively $16.37(0.09)$ and $16.63(0.06) \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and $-14.74(0.28)$ and $-14.21(0.18) \text{ cal K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The negative entropy of activation is consistent with an associative transition state as stylised in **16** which is constructed in the light of previous work from this laboratory⁹. In **16** the full and broken lines, respectively, represent coordinate covalent bonds and weak links. Following attack on π^* (ReO) orbitals by the phosphine lone pair (**16a**), the π -bonds are weakened and a $\text{O}\cdots\text{P}$ link is

Table 3. Rate constants for the reaction $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})] + \text{PPh}_2\text{R} \rightarrow [\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_2\text{R})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ in dichloromethane solution^{a,b}

R	T (K)	$10^2 [\text{PPh}_3]$	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	$10^3 k (\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$
Ph	302	1.06	5.02	4.75(0.02)
		1.40	6.53	
		2.00	9.47	
	305	1.06	6.47	6.16(0.03)
		1.40	8.53	
		2.00	12.25	
	308	1.06	8.17	7.99(0.01)
		1.40	10.92	
		2.00	15.69	
Me	302	1.15	63.02	54.24(0.54)
		1.60	87.03	
		2.00	109.13	

^aThe initial concentration of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ is $1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. ^bLeast-squares deviations are given in parentheses.

Table 4. Rate constants for the reaction $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})] + \text{PPh}_2\text{R} \rightarrow [\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_2\text{R})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ in dichloromethane solution^{a,b}

R	T (K)	$10^2 [\text{PPh}_3]$	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	$10^3 k (\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$
Ph	302	1.06	4.17	4.07(0.01)
		1.40	5.56	
		2.00	8.00	
	305	1.06	5.55	5.28(0.01)
		1.40	7.29	
		2.00	10.46	
	308	1.06	6.95	6.87(0.01)
		1.40	9.35	
		2.00	13.42	
Me	302	1.15	51.82	45.16(0.54)
		1.60	71.75	
		2.00	90.22	

^aThe initial concentration of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ is $1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. ^bLeast-squares deviations are given in parentheses.

established (**16b**, transition state). In the end, the P=O bond remains coordinated to the metal as **16c**.

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Qualitatively consistent with the heteroatom electronegativity ($\text{O} > \text{S}$), the rate of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ is 20% higher than that of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$. Increase in phosphine basicity ($\text{PPh}_2\text{Me} > \text{PPh}_3$) strongly augments the rate. The

rates for the present complexes are higher than those of pyridylazole⁷ species which has one heteroatom(N) less.

Twin isomerization :

The spontaneous twin isomerization reaction of eq. (4) (where $\text{L} = \text{pyod/pytd}$) was studied spectrophotometrically in dichloromethane solution. A representative time evolution spectra is shown in Fig. 4. The reaction followed a first-order rate law eq. (5) implying that the

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{ti}} [\text{Re}(\text{OPxP})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})] \quad (5)$$

reaction is intramolecular. Rate data are listed in Table 5. The rate constants for $x = 1$ complexes followed Eyring

Fig. 4. Time evolution spectra for the twin isomerization reaction of $[\text{Re}(\text{OP1P})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ in CH_2Cl_2 solution at 308 K (A_t is absorbance).

equation and the activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are respectively $16.10(0.10)$ kcal mol $^{-1}$ and $-23.09(0.32)$ cal K $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$ for L = pyod and $16.37(0.20)$ kcal mol $^{-1}$ and $-23.54(0.65)$ cal K $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$ for L = pytd.

It is logical to assume that the isomerization process

is initiated via nucleophilic attack of the metal by the dangling phosphorus atom. The isomerization rates of the pyod complexes are systematically higher than those of the pytd species in agreement with heteroatom electronegativity order ($\text{O} > \text{S}$) which makes the metal more susceptible to attack in the pyod complexes. The attack is stylized in 17. The transformation can then proceed via edge displacement^{15,16}, of a chloride ligand resulting in relay substitutions : Re-OP by Re-Cl and Re-Cl by Re-P. The net effect is twin isomerization. The process depicted in 17 evidently involves considerable ordering consistent with the large negative entropy of activation.

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As in a previous study from this laboratory⁸ the rate of twin isomerization reaction decreases rapidly as the spacer length increases from $x = 1$ to $x = 4$. Indeed the dependence of rate on x is exponential to a good degree as illustrated in the plots of Fig. 5. The data fits approxi-

Table 5. Rate constants for the reaction $[\text{Re}(\text{OPxP})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})] \rightarrow [\text{Re}(\text{PxPO})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})]$ in dichloromethane solution^a

L	x	T (K)	$10^4 [\text{Re}(\text{OPxP})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})] (M)$	$10^5 k_{11} (s^{-1})$	
pyod	1	308	1.25	18.47(0.03)	
	1	308	2.50	18.50(0.04)	
	1	308	3.75	18.48(0.04)	
	1	305	1.25	14.37(0.02)	
	1	302	1.25	11.12(0.04)	
	2	308	1.25	8.92(0.04)	
	3	308	1.25	3.50(0.01)	
	4	308	1.25	1.17(0.01)	
	pytd	1	308	1.25	15.63(0.02)
		1	308	2.50	15.60(0.02)
1		308	3.75	15.67(0.03)	
1		305	1.25	12.02(0.02)	
1		302	1.25	9.33(0.03)	
2		308	1.25	7.53(0.03)	
3		308	1.25	2.83(0.01)	
4		308	1.25	1.05(0.01)	

^aLeast-squares deviations are given in parentheses.

Fig 5 Exponential plot of rate constant versus diphosphine spacer length for the isomerization reaction of $[\text{Re}(\text{OPxP})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})]$ in CH_2Cl_2 solution at 308 K. The pyod and pytd complexes are represented by (●) and (□) respectively

mately with the relation given in eq (6) where A_0 is a constant characteristic of the

$$k_{\text{ti}} = A_0 e^{-ax} \quad (6)$$

pyod and pytd systems. The values of the constants derived from the fits are $A_0 = 0.000413$ and 0.000353 and $a = 0.7997$ and 0.8056 in the cases of pyod and pytd systems respectively. The number of possible conformations of the dangling $(\text{CH}_2)_x\text{PPh}_2$ fragment is indeed expected to increase exponentially as x increases¹⁷, but only a few of the conformations will be spatially suited (proximal metal and phosphine sites) for the reaction to occur.

Lastly we note that the oxidised complex $[\text{Re}^{\text{IV}}(\text{OP1P})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})]\text{ReO}_4$ fails to undergo twin isomerization and is stable in solution. The probable reason of this inertness of the d^3 system has been discussed elsewhere⁸.

Conclusion

The oxorhenium(v) pyridyldiazole chelates of type $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{L})]$ ($\text{L} = \text{pyod}/\text{pytd}$) are shown to undergo facile oxygen atom transfer to both monophosphines and diphosphines furnishing corresponding phosphine oxide complexes of trivalent rhenium which are chemically oxidised to rhenium(IV) congeners. Displacement of coordinated phosphine oxide by phosphine is attended with *meridional* \rightarrow *facial* geometrical isomerization. In the case of diphosphine complexes the displacement is intramolecular and the net process is expressed as a twin isomerization. In $[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_2)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]^+$ the observed Re-O/Re-Cl lengths are shorter and Re-N lengths are longer than those in rhenium(III) analogues consistent with the relative σ and π character of the two oxidation states.

The rates and activation parameters of the bimolecular oxygen atom transfer process have been quantitated. The entropy of activation is negative consistent with an associative transition state which has been modeled. The rate orders $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})] > [\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ and $\text{PPh}_2\text{Me} > \text{PPh}_3$ are consistent with heteroatom electronegativity and phosphine basicity order. The twin isomerization process is unimolecular and is associated with considerable ordering in the transition state (large negative entropy of activation) and a reaction pathway has been proposed. The rate of twin isomerization exponentially decreases with increase in spacer length consistent with the conformational statistics of the spacer.

Experimental

Materials

$[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ and $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ complexes were prepared by reported methods². The purification and drying of dichloromethane and acetonitrile for spectral and electrochemical work were done as before¹⁸. Benzene was distilled over sodium before use. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used as received.

Physical measurements

UV-vis spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UVPC 1601 spectrometer fitted with thermostated cell compartments. IR spectra ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded in KBr disk with the help of a Nicolet Magna IR 750 Series II spectrometer. Proton NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker FT 300 MHz spectrometer. The atom numbering scheme used in ^1H NMR is the same as in crystallography. Spin-spin structures are abbreviated as follows: s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet; and b, broad. Electrochemical measurements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere on a CHI 620 A electrochemical analyzer, using a platinum working electrode. The supporting electrolyte was tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP), and potentials are referred to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE) without junction correction. Solution electrical conductivity was measured in methanol with a Phillips PR 9500 bridge using a platinumized electrode (cell constant of 1.05).

Synthesis of complexes

$[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_2\text{R})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})]$ 4,5 The four phosphine oxide complexes were prepared by a general procedure: reaction of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{L})]$ with excess of PPh_2R in dichloromethane solution. Details are given below for a representative case.

[Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)] To a solution of [ReOCl₃(pyod)] (66 mg, 0.12 mmol) in 25 mL dichloromethane was added 63 mg (0.24 mmol) of PPh₃. The resulting solution was magnetically stirred for 4 h at room temperature and during this time the solution colour changed from orange yellow to violet. The solution was subjected to chromatography on a silica gel column (25 × 1 cm, 60–120 mesh). Excess PPh₃ was eluted out with benzene. The violet band that followed was eluted with a benzene-acetonitrile (25 : 2) mixture. Solvent removal from the eluate under reduced pressure afforded [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)] as a violet solid. Yield 70 mg (73%). Anal Calcd for C₃₀H₂₃Cl₃N₄O₂Re C, 45.32, H, 2.92, N, 7.05. Found C, 45.38, H, 2.99, N, 7.13. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 810^s (650), 719 (1790), 575^s (1150), 477 (2170), 379^s (2340). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1121. ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pyod, 27.31 (1H, b), 22.27 (1H, b), 10.01 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 9.47 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz), 9.05 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz), 6.83 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz), 6.39 (1H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 0.87 (1H, b), PPh₃, 6.50 (6H, m), 7.53 (6H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.08 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz). *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.31 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)] Yield 75%. Anal Calcd for C₃₀H₂₃Cl₃N₄OPSRe C, 44.42, H, 2.86, N, 6.91. Found C, 44.47, H, 2.89, N, 6.97. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 823 (3210), 756 (3720), 590 (2830), 493 (4840), 422^s (3430), 389^s (5060). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1129. ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pytd, 26.93 (1H, b), 23.66 (1H, b), 10.02 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 9.48 (1H, t, *J* 8.2 Hz), 9.04 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.38 (1H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz), -1.49 (1H, b), PPh₃, 6.50 (6H, m), 7.50 (6H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.08 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz). *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.30 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re(OPiP)Cl₃(pyod)] Yield 63%. Anal Calcd for C₃₇H₃₀N₄O₂P₂Cl₃Re C, 48.45, H, 3.30, N, 6.11. Found C, 48.39, H, 3.34, N, 6.16. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 809^s (720), 721 (1900), 578^s (1210), 479 (2390), 377^s (2580), 304 (29310). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1122. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.29 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re(OP3P)Cl₃(pyod)] Yield 67%. Anal Calcd for C₃₉H₃₄N₄O₂P₂Cl₃Re C, 49.56, H, 3.63, N, 5.93. Found C, 49.61, H, 3.57, N, 5.86. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 806^s (790), 716 (2030), 578^s (1290), 477 (2610), 379^s (2650), 303 (32800). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1123. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE,

CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.30 V (ΔE_p = 85 mV).

[Re(OPiP)Cl₃(pytd)] Yield 65%. Anal Calcd for C₃₇H₃₀N₄OP₂SCl₃Re C, 47.62, H, 3.24, N, 6.00. Found C, 47.69, H, 3.19, N, 6.07. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 829 (2290), 755 (2680), 595 (2060), 492 (3490), 421^s (2680), 392^s (3800), 312 (22340). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1122. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.28 V (ΔE_p = 90 mV).

[Re(OP2P)Cl₃(pytd)] Yield 67%. Anal Calcd for C₃₈H₃₂N₄OP₂SCl₃Re C, 48.18, H, 3.40, N, 5.91. Found C, 48.26, H, 3.45, N, 5.83. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 828 (2500), 756 (2920), 596 (2210), 492 (3810), 421^s (2880), 390^s (4190), 312 (24900). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1121. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.28 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re^{IV}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(L)]ReO₄ 8/9 The same general method was used for the synthesis of the two rhenium(IV) phosphine oxide complexes and details are given below for [Re^{IV}(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄. To a solution of [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)] (111 mg, 0.14 mmol) in 20 mL acetonitrile was added dilute aqueous HNO₃ (0.1 M, 5 mL) and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 0.25 h. During this time the solution colour changed from violet to yellow. Solvent removal under reduced pressure afforded [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]ReO₄ as a yellow solid. The solid was washed thoroughly with water to remove the adherent nitric acid and then dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂. Yield 53 mg (69%). Anal Calcd for C₃₀H₂₃N₄O₅PSCl₃Re₂ C, 33.95, H, 2.18, N, 5.28. Found C, 33.91, H, 2.24, N, 5.33. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 428 (720), 361^s (1980), 313 (9620). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1120. ν_{ReO_4} (ReO₄⁻), 904. ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pytd, 60.31 (1H), 10.39 (2H), 8.99 (1H), 3.01 (2H), -70.88 (1H), -94.89 (1H), PPh₃, 9.69 (6H), 6.91 (6H), 6.57 (3H). *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.30 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV) Λ_M = 107 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹.

[Re(OPiP)Cl₃(pyod)]ReO₄ Yield 68%. Anal Calcd for C₃₇H₃₀N₄O₆P₂Cl₃Re₂ C, 38.07, H, 2.59, N, 4.80. Found C, 38.13, H, 2.52, N, 4.74. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) 440 (650), 360^s (2040), 315 (9740). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) $\nu_{O=P}$, 1120. ν_{ReO_4} (ReO₄⁻), 908. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.29 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV) Λ_M = 106 Ω^{-1} cm² M⁻¹.

[Re(PPh₂R)Cl₃(L)]. **12,13** The four complexes were prepared by the same general procedure. Details are given below for [Re(PPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)]. To a solution of [Re(OPPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)] (72 mg, 0.09 mmol) in 30 mL benzene was added PPh₃ (142 mg, 0.54 mmol), and the mixture was heated to reflux for 2 h. The resulting solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue was washed several times with hexane (to remove excess PPh₃). The residue was dissolved in 5 mL dichloromethane and was subjected to chromatography on a silica gel column. A green band was eluted with a benzene-acetonitrile (25 : 10) mixture. Solvent removal from the eluate under reduced pressure afforded [Re(PPh₃)Cl₃(pyod)] as a green solid. Yield : 60 mg (85%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₃N₄OPCl₃Re : C, 46.25; H, 2.98; N, 7.19. Found : C, 46.18; H, 3.06; N, 7.27. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 668 (1430), 588^s (1330), 517^s (1630), 449^s (2790), 389^s (5210), 308 (21250). ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pyod, 21.12 (1H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), 19.49 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 17.27 (1H, d, *J* 5.7 Hz), 10.05 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 6.79 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 2.24 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), -2.51 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz); PPh₃, 14.61 (6H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 10.09 (6H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 9.72 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz). *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.65 V (ΔE_p = 70 mV).

[Re(PPh₃)Cl₃(pytd)]. Yield : 81%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₃N₄SCl₃PRe : C, 45.32; H, 2.92; N, 7.05. Found : C, 45.37; H, 2.96; N, 7.09. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 694 (1760), 594 (1450), 460 (1900), 392 (3250), 315 (19800). ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pytd, 19.82 (1H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), 18.19 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 15.98 (1H, d, *J* 5.7 Hz), 8.75 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 6.12 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 5.49 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz), 0.94 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), -3.81 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz); PPh₃, 13.32 (6H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 8.80 (6H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 8.42 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz). *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.65 V (ΔE_p = 75 mV).

[Re(PxPO)Cl₃(L)]. **14,15** The eight complexes were prepared by the same general procedure which consisted of simply leaving a dichloromethane solution of [Re(OPxP)Cl₃(L)] to isomerize at room temperature (~298 K) in a stoppered flask for 1 (*x* = 1) and 2 (*x* = 2) days for L = pyod complexes and for 1.5 (*x* = 1) and 5 (*x* = 3) days for L = pytd complexes respectively. Procedural details are given for [Re(PIPO)Cl₃(pytd)]. A 80 mg (0.09 mmol) sample of [Re(OP1P)Cl₃(pytd)] was dissolved in 25 mL of dichloromethane, and the solution was left for 36 h. It was then subjected to chromato-

graphy on a silica gel column. A green band was eluted with a benzene-acetonitrile (25 : 10) mixture. Solvent removal under reduced pressure afforded [Re(P1PO)Cl₃(pytd)] as a green solid. Yield : 70 mg (88%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₀N₄OP₂SCl₃Re : C, 47.62; H, 3.24; N, 6.00. Found : C, 47.69; H, 3.31; N, 6.08. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 701 (1640), 589 (1340), 460 (1740), 390 (2970), 314 (17430). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) : $\nu_{O=P}$ (uncoordinated), 1187. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : Re^{IV}-Re^{III}, 0.64 V (ΔE_p = 90 mV).

[Re(P1PO)Cl₃(pyod)]. Yield : 89%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₀N₄O₂P₂Cl₃Re : C, 48.45; H, 3.30; N, 6.11. Found : C, 48.54; H, 3.33; N, 6.02. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 671 (1650), 581 (1540), 511^s (2060), 449^s (3330), 391 (6100), 308 (20890). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) : $\nu_{O=P}$ (uncoordinated), 1187. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : 0.63 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re(P2PO)Cl₃(pyod)]. Yield : 85%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₃₂N₄O₂P₂Cl₃Re : C, 49.01; H, 3.46; N, 6.02. Found : C, 49.06; H, 3.49; N, 6.07. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 660 (1400), 585 (1260), 512^s (1660), 445^s (2780), 385 (5000), 308 (18030). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) : $\nu_{O=P}$ (uncoordinated), 1187. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : 0.64 V (ΔE_p = 80 mV).

[Re(P3PO)Cl₃(pytd)]. Yield : 82%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₉H₃₄N₄OP₂SCl₃Re : C, 48.73; H, 3.56; N, 5.83. Found : C, 48.77; H, 3.64; N, 5.76. UV-vis (λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 699 (1700), 591 (1430), 460 (1610), 393 (2460), 316 (16320). IR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk) : $\nu_{O=P}$ (uncoordinated), 1188. *E*_{1/2} (versus SCE, CH₃CN, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) : 0.64 V (ΔE_p = 75 mV).

Rate measurements for oxygen atom transfer reaction :

The representative case of the reaction of [ReOCl₃(pyod)] with PPh₃ will be described. A known excess of PPh₃ was added to a solution of [ReOCl₃(pyod)] (1.25 × 10⁻⁴ M) in dichloromethane at the desired temperature, and the thermostated reaction was followed spectrophotometrically (quartz cell, path length 1 cm) by measuring the absorbance (*A*_{*t*}) of the peak at 720 nm as a function of time, *t*. The absorbance *A* _{α} at the end of the reaction (24 h) was also measured. Values of *k*_{obs} and *k* were obtained from the slopes of the linear plots of -ln(*A* _{α} - *A*_{*t*}) versus *t* and *k*_{obs} versus [PPh₃] respectively. The activation enthalpy and entropy parameters were de-

terminated from the linear plot of $-\ln[kh/k_B T]$ versus T^{-1} using the Eyring equation (eq. (7)), where k = rate constant, k_B = Boltzman constant, T = temperature, h = Plank constant,

$$k = (k_B T/h) [\exp(-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT) \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R)] \quad (7)$$

R = molar gas constant, ΔH^\ddagger = activation enthalpy and ΔS^\ddagger = activation entropy.

Rate measurements for twin isomerization reaction :

The rate of the twin isomerization process of eq. (4) was also followed spectrophotometrically in dichloromethane solution. Time dependent absorbances A_t were measured at 576 nm and 587 nm for the pyod and pytd complexes respectively and A_α values were obtained at the end of the reaction (1 to 7 days depending on L and x). Rate constants were determined from the linear plots of $-\ln(A_t - A_\alpha)$ versus t . Variable concentration ($1-4 \times 10^{-4} M$) studies carried out in the cases of $x = 1$ revealed that the rate constants were independent of concentration consistent with first-order kinetics. Variable temperature (302–308 K) rate constants were determined in the cases of $x = 1$ and the activation enthalpy and entropy parameters were determined from the linear plot of $-\ln[k_t h/k_B T]$ versus T^{-1} using Eyring equation (eq. (7)). The plot of rate constants against diphosphine spacer length (x) follows a single exponential decay pattern (Fig. 5) with reduced χ^2 values of $\sim 10^{-7}$ and $\sim 10^{-8}$ for pyod and pytd complexes respectively.

The calculations were performed using Microcal Origin V 2.8 (E. Northampton, Microcal Origin Inc., 1991) and Graft, Data Analysis & Graphics Program, V 3.00 (R. J. Leatherbarrow, Erithacus Software Ltd., 1992).

X-Ray structure determination :

Single crystals of the complex $[\text{Re}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]\text{ReO}_4$ were grown by slow diffusion of hexane in dichloromethane solution of the compound. Data were collected on a Nicolet R3m/V four circle diffractometer with graphite-monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) by the ω -scan technique in the range $3^\circ \leq 2\theta < 50^\circ$. All data were corrected for Lorentz-polarization and absorption¹⁹. The metal atoms were located from Patterson maps and the rest of the non-hydrogen atoms emerged from successive Fourier syntheses. The structure was then full-matrix least-squares procedure on F^2 . All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically and hydrogen atoms were included in calculated positions. Calculations were performed using the SHELXTLTM V

5.03 program package²⁰.

Crystallographic data for the complex has been deposited to Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre : CCDC reference number is 612008. The data can be obtained free of charge from Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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